

Conceptual Analysis of Student-Centred Learning

Author(s), OSENI, Rukayat Ejide (RN, BNSc), ADEJUMO, Prisca Olabisi (RN, PhD, FWACN), KOLAWOLE, Ifeoluwapo Oluwafunke (RN, MSc)

Abstract:

Students learn from their teachers in various ways, but student-centred-learning is more unique because it is not teacher-centred. This paper critically examined student centred learning as it focuses the development of learner autonomy and independence by putting task for learning path in the hands of students, inculcating in to them skills, and the basis of how to learn a specific subject and schemata needed to measure up to the specific performance requirement. Constructive interdependence, personal accountability, promotive interaction, suitable use of social skills, and cluster processing are its five essential components. The methods of student centred learning ranges from jigsaw, choice boards, inquiry based, personalized learning, problem based learning, flipped classroom among others. A thorough review of nursing core curriculum is therefore recommended at undergraduate and postgraduate levels by the board members of NMCN, to ensure the inclusion of student-centred learning in order to provide adequate, relevant and appropriate information and subsequently equip nurses to effectively discharge their duties.

Keywords: Student-centred learning, conceptual analysis,

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About Author

Author(s):

OSENI, Rukayat Ejide (RN, BNSc)

Department of Nursing,
Faculty of Clinical Sciences,
University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

ADEJUMO, Prisca Olabisi (RN, PhD, FWACN)

Department of Nursing,
Faculty of Clinical Sciences,
University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

And

KOLAWOLE, Ifeoluwapo Oluwafunke (RN, MSc)

Department of Nursing,
Faculty of Clinical Sciences,
University of Ibadan, Nigeria.

1.0 Introduction

The educational system as a whole is one which has undergone important changes since the last 50 years or so. Traditional educational system has been very teacher-centred, with teachers offering direct instruction with little or no opportunity for student engagement opportunities or empowerment during learning. Over the last ten years, the traditional classroom model has altered dramatically with a change in the model of content delivery, teachers today use various student-centred learning strategies to equip, prepare, and produce students that are able to succeed after graduation (Mcmillan, 2020).

Student-centred learning, also known as learner-centred education, majorly embraces methods of teaching that alters the focus of instruction from the teacher to the student. In original usage, student-centred learning focus the development of learner autonomy and independence by putting task for learning path in the hands of students by inculcating in to them skills, and the basis on how to learn a specific subject and schemata needed to measure up to the specific performance requirement (Jay, 2016).

Student-centred learning permits students to actively partake in their learning. In a student-centred classroom, the target of activity is the student. This means that learners are motivated to partake in a series of tasks including speaking, listening, writing and collaboration with other students. Instead of sitting in the class copying from a book, or listening passively to a teacher, student-centred learning stimulates the student to be actively engaged in their learning, and can promote higher engagement and stimulation in the classroom (i-to-i). In a student-centred method of learning, classrooms move from direct instruction to a more community-driven environment, one which aids student empowerment, communications, critical thinking skills, independence, and problem-solving techniques. In student-centred classrooms, the change commences with the teacher. Student-centred learning strategies do need and involve students in the overall planning process, implementation, and evaluations (Mcmillan, 2020).

Student-centred learning firstly attends to students' interests, recognizing student voice as pivotal to the learning experience. In a student-centred learning space, students choose what they will learn, how they will pace their learning, and how they will assess their own learning by playing the role of the facilitator of the classroom. This is in contrast to traditional education, also dubbed "teacher-centred learning", which situates the teacher as the primarily "active" role while students take a more "passive", receptive role. In a teacher-centred classroom, teachers choose what the students will learn, how the students will learn, and how the students will be assessed on their learning. In contrast, student-centred learning needs students to be active, responsible participants in their own learning and with their own pace of learning.

Accordingly, a conspicuous pedagogy will be teacher-as-coach, to motivate students to learn how to learn and thus to teach themselves, rather than the more traditional teacher-centred learning with teacher-as-deliverer-of-instructional-services, which places the teacher at its center in an active role and students in a passive, receptive role. This pedagogy acknowledges student voice as pivotal to the learning experience for every learner and needs students to be active, responsible participants in their own learning. To capitalize on this, teaching and learning should be tailored to the maximum feasible scope. Decisions about the

contents of the course of study, the utilization of students' and teachers' time, and the selection of teaching materials and specific pedagogies must be completely placed in the hands of the staff and students.

Source: Student-centred model adopted from Jay (2016)

1.1 Study Objectives

The objective of this study was to examine student centred learning as it focuses on the development of learner autonomy and independence. The study reviewed key elements of successful student-centred learning, methods of student-centred learning, student-centred learning curriculum, and advantages and disadvantages of student-centred learning. Related theories were reviewed and implication to nursing was also considered.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Key Elements of Successful Student-Centred Learning

Five essential components must be existing for a situation to be deemed student-centred learning, they are: constructive interdependence, personal accountability, promotive interaction, suitable use of social skills, and cluster processing (Johnson & Johnson, 2005). These will be discussed in further detail here.

1. **Constructive interdependence:** When a teacher follows constructive interdependence in a group, they are mindful that each individual responsibility has a

solid impression on the group. This identified and improved accountability assists the student's struggle to succeed (Johnson & Johnson, 2005). Likewise, once constructive dependency has been built, learners understand that each member's unique contribution is needed for the entire group to attain its goals (Johnson, Johnson, & Holubec, 1990). Constructive interdependence, according to Johnson and Johnson (1989), can be divided into three subtypes: outcome, means, and boundary. Outcome interdependence is the first sort of interdependence, and it entails actual aims and rewards. Regardless of the way it is done, the building of outcome interdependence is likely to raise levels of productivity and accomplishment (Johnson & Johnson, 2003). The second sort of dependency happens when students are needed to share money, take on various tasks, and finish coursework so as to achieve the group's goals (Gillies, 2007). These approaches, according to Johnson and Johnson (2005), are knotted and inextricably connected. The researchers decided that resources should be split among team members, goals should be assigned to each group member, and segments should be disseminated to increase participants' commitment to the meeting and its goals (Johnson & Johnson, 2005). When working interdependently, the third subtype of interdependence, border interdependence, is useful for building learner connection (Johnson & Johnson, 2005). Furthermore, border dependency may be available without considering unforeseen interludes between individuals who may categorize other people into separate groups (Johnson & Johnson, 2005).

2. **Personal accountability:** Personal accountability is an essential component of successful student-centred learning. This type of task happens when each person's behaviours are assessed against a reliable parameter before being returned to the group and the individual (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). When planned individual accountability is in place, according to Hooper, Ward, Hannafin, and Clark (1989), student-centred learning has a greater rate of achievement. Furthermore, personal task requires pupils to be aware that they are in charge of their tasks to the faction. Scrounging is not allowed because everyone should have a voice in accomplishing the group's goals (Gillies, 2007). When students acquire and share knowledge with their group members, their self-efficacy increases. As a result, students are made to work harder for the team's success (Gillies, 2007). If each student's participation is enforced, there will be no unnecessary aggressive actions, personal tasks will be prioritized, members will feel accountable for the final results and community loafing will end (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). Similarly, the size of the group is important, since the more the group members, the less likely its members are able to identify their individual assistance, reducing the group's chances of succeeding (Kerr, 2001).
3. **Promotive interaction:** Another important component for student-centred learning is cheering interaction (Gillies, 2007). Promotive communication occurs when students have physical contact with one another and observe face-to-face dialogical conversations to evaluate the group's assignment (Gillies, 2007). Promotive communication also happens when students motivate other members in accomplishing the group's goals (Johnson & Johnson, 2008). Johnson and Johnson (2009) added promotive interaction entails learners' sharing resources, believing in

one another, giving successful aid to classmates, staying focused for the group's gain, and ensuring that contemporaries' struggles are valuable in accomplishing the group's goals. Interpersonal collaboration and dealings are the result of learners interacting closely with others and being able to interpret both verbal and nonverbal cues, as well as body language that are necessary for creating individual relationships (Gillies, 2007). Furthermore, the academics argue that providing feedback to peers so as to enhance their work and get their view-points leads to better decision-making and stimulates dialogue (Johnson & Johnson, 2009)

4. **Suitable use of social skills:** For effective student-centred learning to happen, social skills, assignments, and competent group work are needed (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). If the aim is to achieve brilliance via student-centred learning, students must be taught and encouraged to utilize communal and group intelligence (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). For the group to accomplish its universal objectives; members must be bothered about new members in the group and make them comfortable. They must also discover clear solutions to general disagreements, familiarize themselves with and trust other group members, and network effectively. Members must have some of the above-mentioned societal and group capabilities, which eventually consist of the rudimentary connections among them, if they are to effectively operate together and deal with pressure levels (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). According to Archer-Kath, Johnson, and Johnson (1994), improving the output of the group and participants' achievement is more supportive than charitable to the entire group, given that each associate's response about his or her use of planned communal skills is more helpful than charitable to the entire group. Learners must also learn to value turns, make open verdicts, and share resources consistently, according to Gillies (2007). Furthermore, these skills are hard to perfect, especially for various classes who are not usually given the chance to speak with their nobility and are expected to be static receivers of the instruction that happens (Gillies, 2007).
5. **Cluster processing:** Cluster processing is, in the end, a necessary component of student-centred learning. It involves students agreeing on which activities should be modified or maintained, as well as reflections on actions that were either useless or fruitful. Cluster processing is used to analyse and broaden those courses of action that were taken by members, which will help the entire group achieve its objectives (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). Furthermore, cluster processing includes a determining evaluation component since learners try to expand the number of options available to them in order to achieve their goals (Gillies, 2007). It is expected that reflecting on the hard work of other members of the group will result in elements working harder to improve actual or imagined group insufficiencies, hence advancing the entire group's achievement (Williams & Karau, 1991). Furthermore, according to Gillies, cluster processing stimulates members' indications on their roles because they must determine whether any changes need to be made, to combine the cluster activities and, as a result, boost group members' involvement (Gillies, 2007). Cluster processing comprises students asking meta-cognitive form of questions such as, "How are we doing? Is there anything else that we should be doing? What could we do differently?"

(Gillies, 2007). Furthermore, cluster processing nurtures respect among members because each individual activity and attempt towards the cluster is known as a treasured component in accomplishing the end objectives (Smith, Tyler, Huo, Ortiz, & Lind, 1998). When the above-mentioned five basic foundations of collaborative learning are apparent, the group is said to be organized, and when they are not, the clusters are said to be unorganized (Gillies et al., 2008). In order to develop participants' sense of value, cluster leaders must show their admiration of members of the group, verbally (Smith et al., 1998).

2.2 Methods of Students' Centred Learning

1. **Personalized Learning: Personalized learning - is a student specialized approach where the student's interests and culture are considered and merged into their education. While this may surely engage the student in the learning process, it is just one constituent of a fully student-centred approach (Jay, 2016).**
2. **Choice Boards:** Choice boards permit students to choose activities they will complete to practice a skill or display understanding. In this approach to learning, learners are granted ownership and empowerment opportunities while teachers differentiate their instruction. Choice boards can be used not just for assessment purposes, but also to familiarize with new material, for supplemental practice, or as a combination of multiple parts of a lesson or unit.
3. **Jigsaw/Stations/Centers:** The Jigsaw method an older concept, has evolved and been combined into a center/station approach. In its most basic form, this technique involves students using cooperative learning as they search to put the "puzzle" together. Each student is accountable for an individual component of knowledge, then takes knowledge gained and applies it to larger body of work (puzzle). This concept is used at the elementary, middle, and high school level with teachers establishing stations and centers in their classroom to help facilitate the individual or small-group knowledge piece of the Jigsaw strategy, leading to some type of presentation, discussion, competition, or other strategy used to demonstrate learning.
4. **Inquiry-Based Learning:** In this learning strategy, learners' queries, ideas, and analysis are stressed and fostered, focusing on the student perspective regarding a particular open question or problem. This strategy is specifically useful for novel student engagement, leading students to move beyond basic understanding to a deeper understanding of critical thinking, evidence-based reasoning, and creative problem solving. Within inquiry-based learning, various contents of a lesson can be case studies, group projects, and research projects, among others. More in-depth links to the material provide occasions for students to hone skills that are treasurable in the world in which we dwell.
5. **Project-Based Learning and Problem-Based Learning:** Teachers have their own educational jargon, and often-times, you will hear "PBL" used in teacher discussions. Two learning strategies being implemented more often are project-based learning and problem-based learning. In project-based learning, students work on longer tasks that culminate in the creation of an original presentation or product. This learning strategy depends heavily on student collaboration, communication, and creativity, with the

teacher serving as a facilitator student work and progress. Problem-based learning includes shorter projects that examine a current problem, and through definition, research, and causes of the problem, students collaboratively evaluate solutions to the chosen problem, solve the problem, or report potential solutions and/or findings. Both of these learning strategies utilize related, real-life links to the outside world, giving students valuable experience with problem solving and critical thinking opportunities that will behoove them after graduation.

6. **Flipped Classrooms:** Teachers continuously look for ways to make best use of instructional time in the classroom. A learning strategy that considers this is the use of a flipped classroom. In this learning format, novel or introductory content is delivered to learners outside of the classroom, with teachers combining many of the strategies already explained such as choice boards or jigsawing to allow student choice in their learning. Learning material can include readings, videos, pre-recorded presentations or direct instruction, or research assignments (McMillan, 2020).

2.3 Student-centred Learning Curriculum

The curriculum offers a lot of assistance to learners. The curriculum offers students a written fact about the types of learning experiences they need to achieve for accomplishing the expected learning objectives. The curriculum makes them accustomed with the learning goals. This way it makes the tasks of learning goal oriented. This determination makes them driven towards learning as they are conscious of the types of behavioral changes expected as learning outcome from studying a particular subject or doing a certain activity to complement learning.

A properly developed curriculum is followed by the resource materials needed to supplement it. These resources include suggested experiments, learning activities, projects, assignments, references etc. These materials are also important for both teachers and learners. A curriculum is a properly established framework of the teaching-learning process. It includes learning aims that should be known to the learners. When learners are conscious of the learning goals they can plan, execute and evaluate them for the actualization of learning outcome of the course being studied. Hence a properly developed curriculum can assist the learner in their learning process from commencement to end for the realization of the set learning goals. Realization of these learning objectives leads to overall growth and development in all the ramifications and dimensions of their personality.

2.4 Advantages and Disadvantages of Student-Centred Learning

According to Anand (2015), the advantages of student-centred learning are:

1. Improves participation: A learner centred approach attends to all the significant needs of learners, making sure they get a personalized and easy learning experience.
2. Improves retention of knowledge: Given that a learner centred approach places high importance on applicability and engagement, it majorly affects learners' interest levels. The learner centred approach migrates from traditional learning. For example, in developing a course for engineers, the course should have real life scenarios that are relevant to their day-to-day problems. Also, the course will have certain

components, which will ensure they use the knowledge that have been previously acquired This way, learners will retain the knowledge more as opposed to a plain teacher-centred learning course with a lot of theoretical knowledge.

3. Boosts performance at work: A typical learner centred course will have a lot of scenarios, case studies, role plays, etc. For example, if an organization is training its employees on quality guidelines or industry best practices, a learner centred course with a lot of engaging and interactive content will help learners grasp the content more effectively. This way, learners are more likely to relate their learning at work, leading to improved on-the-job performance.
4. Develops problem-solving skills: A learner centred course has many real life examples, including games, quizzes, and challenges. For example, the course may have problems and games involving real life problems, which will enforce learners to think of way out. This kind of training develops problem-solving skills, which is useful when learners encounter similar problems at work.
5. Fosters collaborative learning: Learner centred courses offers the opportunity to foster collaborative learning. It should be organized in such a way that learners have to involve their peers in finishing the course. Alternatively, the courses should have certain group exercises, which makes learners come together to solve problems, and thereby share learning. This approach not only motivates collaboration but also fosters teamwork.
6. Makes learning more fun: Use of games and stories makes learning more fun. A learner centred approach gives a lot of choices to learners. For example, if a particular course involves research, learners should be given opportunity to choose research topics. Likewise, learner centred courses applies lots of different mediums, such as videos, podcasts, practical assignments, role play etc. With these elements, learning will no longer be boring and monotonous.
7. Facilitates personalized learning: All learners do not have the same learning needs. Some may just like to understand the basics of a concept, while some may like to understand a course in detail. Also, some learners may already have some knowledge about a topic, whereas some of them will be entirely new to the concept. A traditional course will treat all learners the same way, and may not respond to the needs of different types of learners. Things are different with learner centred courses.

Other advantages according to physics-catalyst (2021),

1. This approach to curriculum gives power to learners.
2. Students see their needs clearly reflected in the classroom, which is very motivating.
3. It creates a direct link between classwork and the learner's needs.
4. Learners can easily transfer new skills in day to day activities.
5. It encourages learners persistence.

According to Anand (2015), the disadvantages of student-centred learning are:

1. It often depends on the teacher's capability to create materials appropriate to learner's expressed needs.
2. It requires more skill, time and resources on the part of the teacher.

3. It is often uneasy for teachers to make an acceptable balance among competing needs and interests of students.
4. In terms of man, material and resources this approach could be a luxury that learners often cannot afford.

3.0 Relevant Theories

3.1 Constructionism learning theory

Constructionist learning is the formation by learners of mental models to comprehend the world around them. Constructionism sponsors student-centred, discovery learning where learners use what they already know, to gain more knowledge. Students learn via participation in project-based learning where they make connections between different ideas and areas of knowledge facilitated by the teacher through coaching rather than using lectures or step-by-step guidance. Further, constructionism holds that learning can occur most effectively when people are active in making tangible objects in the real world. In this sense, constructionism is linked with experiential learning and builds on Jean Piaget's epistemological theory of constructivism (Wikipedia, 2021).

3.2 Bandura (1977) Social Learning Theory

Cognitive psychology theories play an important role in articulating the link between creative teaching and successful learning outcomes (McInerney & McInerney, 2010). The learner's assiduous effort in generating individual interpretation and thoughtfulness for the knowledge at his disposal is emphasised from cognitive perspectives. It is obvious that resourceful learning happens when people generate their own idea (McInerney & McInerney, 2010). The academic contents planted in the learners' minds and the means by which these contents are expressed in the learners' daily personal bodily interactions with their environment, are the emphasis of a constructivist learning perspective (McInerney & McInerney, 2010). This is characterised as personal constructivism because it unambiguously emphasises that knowing is pro-actively built up by learners' self-discovery and exploration, rather than being taught by others (McInerney & McInerney, 2010).

Bandura's social learning theory emphasises the importance of seeing and modelling other people's attitudes, behaviours, and emotional responses. Bandura (1977) stated that learning would be so uneasy if not harmful, if people had to solely depend on the effect of their own actions to inform them of what to do. Social learning theory explains human behaviour as a constant mutual interaction of cognitive, behavioural, and environmental controls. Fortunately, most human behaviour is absorbed observationally, via replication from witnessing others, and this indirect information serves as action guidance in later contexts.

SLT is arguably the most powerful learning and development theory, ever devised. It is rooted in a lot of classic learning theories' key ideas. Furthermore, because it involves concentration, recollection, and reward, it serves as a bridge between cognitive and behaviourist learning theories (Muro & Jeffrey 2008). Bandura, on the other hand, believes that unequivocal fortification cannot account for all types of learning. This is because, according to his thesis, a social component exists, stating that individuals can learn new

behaviours and information by observing other people. There are three broad main beliefs for learning from each other, according to the rudiments of this idea.

People learn from one another through surveillance, simulation, and modelling, according to Bandura's social learning theory. Because it entails concentration, memory, and impulse, the idea is known as the "bridge" between cognitive and behaviourist learning theories according to the Bobodoll experiment in which children showed an increase in hostility after observing adult behaviour. Examining, simulating, and fortifying are all part of the social learning theory. The notion behind this thesis is that people examine other people's behaviour, compartments and the effects of such manners. In general, human behaviour is nurtured through observation. By modelling the observations of other people, one can create ideal notions of how inventive behaviours are carried out, and this implicit information can then be used as a guide in later situations. The social learning theory seeks to expatiate how people perceive things and what circumstances confirm their actions.

Live models are one of the three forms of modelling stimulus identified by Bandura I.e. Symbolism and Verbal instruction. He went on to say that, in addition to sense of cognition and behavioural practise, the type of model influences observation, which includes concentration, retention, replication, and enthusiasm. The Social learning theory is a group of learning theories, based on the belief that human behaviour is governed by three forms of relationships: cognitive difficulties, environmental control, and manners. The social learning theory justifies human behaviour as a result of a continuous mutual communication between cognitive behaviour and environmental factors (Albert Bandura).

The social learning theory has been grossly applied to the understanding of aggression (Bandura, 1973) and psychological disarrays, particularly in the aspect of behaviour adjustment (Bandura, 1969). It is the theoretical foundation for the behaviour modelling modus operandi, which is widely used in educational programmes. Bandura has focused his research on the concept of self-efficacy in a variety of contexts (e.g., Bandura, 1977). The television industry is one of the most common (and all-encompassing) examples of social learning condition. Commercials promote the purchase of a specific beverage or the use of a particular hair shampoo as a way for people or consumers to become well acquainted with it and in order to gain the approval of attractive people. We may be able to repeat the behaviour seen in the advertisement and buy the goods advertised, depending on the constituent procedure involved (such as curiosity and impulse).

Bandura went on to say that modelling is a way for people to symbolically represent genuine results. The principle of reciprocal determinism, which asserts that just as an individual's behaviour is affected by their surroundings and the surroundings influenced by the individual's behaviour, has been a major component of the social learning theory. In other words, a person's activities, circumstances, and personal characteristics all exert equal power over one another. Someone who plays violent video games, for example, may be able to persuade their peers to join in, which encourages them to play more frequently. Liehert and Sprafking (1988) who used concrete examples of decision-making between gun and butter in a war or peaceful environment; hypothesised that if someone has taken a basic economics course, he is familiar with the principal planner's dilemma of deciding whether to allocate limited resources for guns or butter. Connivers, on the other hand, are people, and most

people arrive at life's war-or-peace decision points having already launched preferred reactions.

4.0 Implication to Nursing

As one of the most trusted professions, nursing has a tremendous task to provide quality care and outcomes. The conceptual review done in this study reveals the implication for nursing education and nursing research.

4.1 Implications to Nursing Education

- a) This study ensured that student-centred learning are included in the education programs for student nurses and healthcare professionals at the postgraduate level by the educational section of the Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria(NMCN) and other Nursing Regulatory Bodies in other countries of the world.
- b) A thorough review of nursing core curriculum can be instigated by this study, both at undergraduate and postgraduate levels by the board members of NMCN, to ensure the inclusion of student-centred learning in order to provide adequate, relevant and appropriate information and subsequently equip nurses to effectively discharge their duties.
- c) Information from this study can be used in identifying the key areas of knowledge deficit which will serve as a framework and structure for the development of appropriate student-centred approaches by the Mandatory Continuing Professional Development Program (MCPDP) committee, as endorsed by NMCN, aimed at improving trainee nurses' knowledge and practice.

4.2 Implications to Nursing Research

- a) The nursing implication of the study lies in the scope for expanding the quality of student-centred learning strategies. In this era of evidence based practice, publication of this research work and other studies on student-centred learning strategies will take nursing to a new horizon.
- b) This research work can initiate evidence based student-centred learning strategies on prompt application in the classroom.

5.0 Conclusion

This study achieved its initial objectives of assessing the efficacy of student-centred learning strategies in the classroom. This study concluded that student-centred learning strategies can benefit nurse trainees therefore, resulting in an increase in knowledge and practice of nursing.

6.0 Recommendations

In view of the findings stated earlier, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Nurse educators should also be encouraged by their institutions to apply student-centred learning strategies in the classroom.
- ii. The government should ensure favorable environment that could motivate the use of student-centred learning strategies in schools of nursing and universities.

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